

**DESCRIPTION OF TWO NEW SUBSPECIES OF *MURICOPSIS*
(*RISOMUREX*) (MURICIDAE: MURICOPSINAE) FROM ANGOLA,
WESTERN AFRICA**

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Introduction: Among the west African Muricidae in MNHN, an ocinebrine species was recently described from Angola (Houart, 1989), and another *Muricopsis* (*Risomurex*) species was described from Senegal (Vokes & Houart 1986). The present paper adds the descriptions of two intertidal/subtidal *Muricopsis* from southern Angola, that are considered geographical subspecies disjunct from the nominal subspecies in senegalese waters.

Muricopsis (*Risomurex*) *fusiformis punctata* n. sp.

Figs. 1-2, 3, 6-7, 8, 9.

Material examined: Angola, prov. Moçamedes: Praia das Conchas, S. Gofas coll., 7 sps; Praia Amelia, on rocks, S. Gofas coll., 28 sps; Chapéu Armado, low tide, on rocks, S. Gofas coll., 15 sps; Praia do Cesar, Lucira, on rocks, S. Gofas coll., 21 sps. Prov. Benguela: Baía de Santa Maria, rocks, 0-2 m, S. Gofas coll., 36 sps (including 18 juveniles of 1-4 mm in length); Baía de Limagen, rocks, 0-2 m, S. Gofas coll., 13 sps (including 9 juveniles of about 1 mm in length). Prov. Bengo: Barra do Dande, rocks, S. Gofas coll., 1 sp. Ile Anne-Bon, San Pedro (= Annobon Id, Gulf of Guinea), Marche-Marchad leg., 1 sh. All MNHN; Lucira Bay, S. Angola, low tide, under rocks, 0-5 m, F. Fernandes coll., 8 sps, coll. R. Houart.

Type material: Holotype and 6 paratypes from the type locality, MNHN; 28 paratypes (19 MNHN, 3 Centro de Zoologia do ICTT, Lisboa, 1 IRSNB n.º 27241, 5 coll. R. Houart), Praia Amelia, Moçamedes, Angola; 15 paratypes MNHN, Chapéu Armado, Moçamedes, Angola; 2 paratypes MNHN, Praia do Cesar, Lucira, Moçamedes, Angola.

Type locality: Praia das Conchas, prov. Moçamedes, Angola, West Africa.

Distribution: Only known from the material examined.

Description: Shell fusiform and heavy. Spire high with 1,5 - 1,75 protoconch whorls and 5-6 convex teleconch whorls. Protoconch sculptured with a duplicate spiral keel.

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Last whorl ornamented with 8-11 axial ribs and 11-14 spiral cords, with 2-3 narrow threads between each pair of cords. Aperture ovate with smooth columellar lip and moderately deep anal notch; outer apertural lip slightly crenulate, inner side with 5 equidistant small denticles. Siphonal canal short, open, and slightly bent dorsally.

Colour of alternatively pale coloured and darker coloured spiral bands: a dark band anteriorly to the suture, generally extending onto the two adapical spiral cords; a paler band situated half of the whorls, and a second darker band just posterior to the suture of whorls. Base of last whorl also darker, extending onto the posterior part of the siphonal canal. Brownish to blackish spots at the intersection of spiral cords and axial ribs, giving the appearance of punctuate coloration.

Typical muricopsine radula, with short and projecting central cusp (fig. 3).

Dimensions: up to 12 mm in length.

Dimensions of the holotype: 12 x 6 mm.

Discussion: *M. fusiformis punctata* is different from *M. fusiformis fusiformis* (Gmelin, 1791) (fig. 13-14), by its coloration and smoother sculpture, consisting of 8-11 axial ribs on the last whorl while regularly of 11-15 in *M. fusiformis fusiformis*. The dark coloured spiral bands are absent in *M. fusiformis fusiformis*, which is paler coloured, mostly uniform, without blackish or brownish spots. *M. fusiformis fusiformis* has a larger size, attaining 15 mm in length for specimens with a same number of teleoconch whorls. It lives from northern Mauritania (MNHN: Baie de l'Etoile) to Senegal, where it is uncommon.

A gap of more than 4000 kms in the geographical distribution is, I think, also significative, because *M. fusiformis fusiformis* is not a rare species and its habitat is well known, living in shallow water in Senegal. The littoral waters of the Ivory Coast, Ghana and Gabon being sufficiently known, the absence of that species in these regions is certainly significative. The protoconch indicates non-planktothrophic larval development, and the distance between both groups of populations (*M. fusiformis fusiformis* and *M. fusiformis punctata*) being very important, genetic exchange between both forms is probably non extant.

To erect this new taxon at species or subspecies level is a matter of personal opinion, but the similarity between the nominal species and *M. fusiformis punctata* incited me to name it as geographical subspecies.

A single, dead collected shell is reported from Annobon, Id., Gulf of Guinea (MNHN). It is a typical *M. fusiformis punctata* with its punctuate coloration, and small size. Although there is no reason to doubt this record, it is to be noted that *M. fusiformis punctata* has not been recorded from the better collected island of São Tomé, and I consider that this Annobon record needs confirmation.

M. suga (Fischer-Piette, 1942) has a narrower and more elongate shell, with an average size of 10 x 4 mm in comparison of the average size of 9, 5 x 5 mm of *M. fusiformis punctata*, *M. suga* has thicker and fewer spiral cords while its protoconch is stouter and not so elongate.

Muricopsis (Risomurex) suga discissus n. sp.

Figs. 4-5, 10-12.

Material examined: Angola, prov. Benguela: Baia de Santa Maria, rocks, 0-2 m, S. Gofas coll., 10 sps; Caota, rocks, 0-2 m, S. Gofas coll., 23 sps (including 11 juveniles of less than 3 mm in length); prov. Luanda: Futungo, Bay of Mussulo, low tide, S. Gofas coll., 16 sps and shs; Bay of Corimba, rocks, 0-1 m, S. Gofas coll., 3 sps; Bay of Corimba, dredgings, 10-20 m, S. Gofas coll., 4 sps. All MNHN.

Type material: Holotype and 9 paratypes from the type locality, MNHN; 23 paratypes (17 MNHN, 2 Centro de Zoologia do ICTT, Lisboa, 1 IRSNB n.º 27241; 3 coll., R. Houart), Caota, prov. Benguela, Angola, 0-2 m, on rocks.

Type locality: Baia de Santa Maria, on rocks, 0-2 m, prov. Benguela, Angola.

Distribution: Only known from the material examined.

Description: Shell fusiform, narrowly elongate, Spire very high, with 1,5 protoconch whorls and 5-6 convex teleoconch whorls, Protoconch sculptured with a duplicate spiral keel.

Last whorl ornamented with 9-11 axial ribs and 9-10 spiral cords, with 2-3 narrow threads between each pair of cords. Aperture ovate; anal notch deep; columellar lip slightly erect, bearing 2 small denticles anteriorly. Inner side of outer apertural lip with 5 strong denticles. Siphonal canal short, open and slightly bent dorsally.

Shell uniformly light brown or dark brown coloured; darker coloration at the intersection of axial ribs and spiral cords. Aperture brownish.

Dimensions: up to 12,9 mm in length.

Dimensions of the holotype: 11 x 4 mm.

Discussion: *M. suga discissus* differs from the nominal subspecies (fig. 15) by its more numerous spiral sculpture, consisting of 7-9 cords in *M. suga suga*, while *M. suga discissus* regularly has 9-10 cords. The spiral threads, 2-3 in *M. suga discissus*, are more numerous (3-4) in the nominal subspecies. The protoconch of *M. suga discissus* is more elongate and narrower.

M. fusiformis punctata is broader with a punctuate coloration and shallower spiral cords.

M. suga discissus is here described as subspecies of *M. suga* for the same reasons as those given for *M. fusiformis fusiformis* and *fusiformis punctata*. The known geographical range of *M. suga suga* is restricted to Senegal.

Fig. 1-2 — Protoconch of *M. (R) fusiformis punctata* n.ssp. (scale bar: 0,5 mm).

Fig. 3 — Radula of *M. (R) fusiformis punctata* n.ssp. (scale bar: 10 mm).

Fig. 4-5 — Protoconch of *M. (R) fusiformis discissus* n.ssp. (scale bar: 0,5 μ).

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- Fig. 6-7 — *Muricopsis (Risomurex) fusiformis punctata* n.ssp., holotype MNHN, 12 mm.
- Fig. 8 — *M. (R) fusiformis punctata*, n.ssp. paratype MNHN, 10 mm.
- Fig. 9 — *Muricopsis (Risomurex) punctata* n.ssp., holotype MNHN, 12 mm. Whitenened.
- Fig. 10-12 — *Muricopsis (Risomurex) suga discissus* n.ssp., holotype MNHN, 11 mm. (Figure 12 whitened).
- Fig. 13-14 — *M. (R) fusiformis fusiformis* (Gmelin, 1791), lectotype MNHN, 13,6 mm. (Figure 14 whitened).
- Fig. 15 — *Muricopsis (Risomurex) suga* (Fisher-Piette, 1942), lectotype MNHN, 10,3 mm. Whitenened.

